

UNIVERSITET BITIRUVCHILARINING KOMPETENSIYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA BAHOLASH MODELLARI VA ALGORITMLARI

Parmankulov Farxod Nurali o'g'li

Toshkent shahridagi Belarus-O'zbekiston qo'shma tarmoqlararo amaliy texnik kvalifikatsiyalar instituti

e-mail: farxodparmonqulov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14913075>

Annotatsiya: maqolada yo'naltirilgan vaznli grafik shaklida taqdim etilgan kompetensiyaning kognitiv modeli qurilgan, kompetensiyaning tizimli xususiyatlari ta'kidlangan, bu kompetensiyani yaxlitlikka o'rganishga va o'rganilgan fanlarning ahamiyatlilik darajasini axborot entropiyasi asosida aniqlashga imkon beradi, kognitiv model asosida integral mezondan foydalangan holda kompetensiya darajasini baholash tartibi ishlab chiqilgan. ma'lum bir vaqtda fanlarni o'zlashtirish darajasi va ularning kompetensiyani shakllantirishga ta'siri darajasi, uch bosqichdan iborat kompetensiyaning hayotiy tsikli tushunchasi kiritildi, ularning har biri uchun universitetning reyting tizimining ball baholari asosida kompetensiyani shakllantirish darajasini monitoring qilish algoritmi ishlab chiqilgan, asosiy o'quv dasturini amalga oshirishni rejalashtirish va monitoring qilishning mavjud tizimini qayta qurish bo'yicha tavsiyalar to'plami taklif qilingan. universitetni boshqarishning avtomatlashtirilgan tizimlarida ishlatiladigan dasturiy modullarning funktsional imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion jarayonlar, kompetensiyaga asoslangan yondashuv, boshqaruv moslamasi, axborot resurslari, kognitiv model, vaznli grafik, axborot xavfsizligi, juftlik taqqoslash usuli, baholash matritsasi.

МОДЕЛИ И АЛГОРИТМЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И ОЦЕНКИ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ ВЫПУСКНИКА ВУЗА

Парманкулов Фархад Нурали ўғли

Совместный Белорусско-Узбекский межотраслевой институт прикладных технических квалификаций
в городе Ташкенте

e-mail: farxodparmonqulov@gmail.com

Аннотация: в статье построена когнитивная модель компетенции, представленная в виде ориентированного взвешенного графа, выделены системные характеристики компетенции, позволяющие исследовать компетенцию на целостность и определять степень значимости изученных дисциплин на основе информационной энтропии, на основе когнитивной модели разработана процедура оценки уровня компетенции, использующая интегральный критерий, с учетом уровня усвоения дисциплин в заданный момент времени и степени их влияния на формирование компетенции, введено понятие жизненного цикла компетенции состоящего из трёх этапов, для каждого из которых разработан алгоритм мониторинга уровня формирования компетенции на основе балльных оценок рейтинговой системы вуза, предложена совокупность рекомендаций по реструктуризации существующей системы планирования и мониторинга реализации основной образовательной программы, расширяющих функциональность программных модулей, используемых в автоматизированных системах управления вузом.

Ключевые слова: инновационные процессы, компетентностный подход, управляющее устройство, информационные ресурсы, когнитивная модель, взвешенный граф, информационная безопасность, метод парных сравнений, оценочная матрица.

MODELS AND ALGORITHMS FOR ESTABLISHING AND EVALUATING GRADUATE COMPETENCIES AT UNIVERSITIES

Farkhad Parmankulov Nurali o'g'li

Joint Belarusian-Uzbek Intersectoral Institute of Applied Technical Qualifications in Tashkent

e-mail: farxodparmonqulov@gmail.uz

Annotation: The article presents a cognitive model of competence in the form of an oriented weighted graph, identifies systemic characteristics of competence, and uses information entropy to determine the degree

of significance of the studied disciplines. Based on the cognitive model, a procedure for assessing the level of competence has been developed using an integral criterion, which takes into account the degree of assimilation of disciplines at a given point in time and the degree of their influence on the formation of competence. It also introduces the concept of the life cycle of competence, which consists of three stages, for each of which an algorithm has been developed tracking the degree of competency development. A set of suggestions is put forth to restructure the current system of planning and overseeing the execution of the primary educational program, as well as to increase the functionality of software modules utilized in automated university management systems, based on the scoring evaluations of the university rating system.

Keywords: cognitive model, information resources, control device, paired comparison method, evaluation matrix, innovative processes, competency approach, and information security.

1. Introduction.

In light of the revised standards for graduate training quality in the context of the switch to the Regional State Educational Standards of Higher Professional Education (RSES HPE), it is crucial to plan the process of training a specialist in order to acquire the requisite competencies. All higher education institutions' educational policies and practices are being reorganized in line with the competency approach since the new RSES HPE was introduced. These modifications are predicated on the notion that a university graduate's degree of training will now be evaluated by measuring his competencies.

The teaching staff's increasingly global goals are established by innovative processes in domestic education: giving students a set of capabilities that will raise their level of competence. This is outlined in the State Target Program for the Development of Education, which was authorized by the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Resolution. Its primary objective is to guarantee that the prerequisites for fulfilling the demands of the labor market, society, and citizens in terms of high-quality education are met. A higher education institution guarantees the quality of student training, according to the RGOS HPE, in part by "developing objective procedures for assessing the level of knowledge and skills of students, and the competencies of graduates"[1-5].

2 Technology for obtaining materials and research method

Universities are now establishing education quality control departments, but the instruments for efficiently organizing and assessing the process of developing specialists' abilities and the variables affecting them are still insufficiently advanced. We have examined the ideas of competence and competency and identified the elements that shaped them over the university education period. The challenge of creating a competency passport in order to have a clear grasp of its structure and content is described. There is evidence to support the need for a competency model. Through the study of disciplines, an assumption is established regarding the development of competence during the university study term.

Shows the block diagram of the administration of the training organization from the perspective of the competence approach. The techniques for measuring f and y are denoted by D_f and D_y , while f represents the state of the factors influencing competence and y by the degree of competence. In order to accomplish aim Z_2 , or to form the necessary degree of competence, the control device (CD), after receiving information on the states of f and y at the input, forms the control action U . $(f, y^{\wedge}(\cdot), Z^{\wedge}) \rightarrow U \rightarrow Y^{\wedge} \cdot Y^{\wedge*}$ Research on the degree to which disciplines influence the construction of competence is lacking, as is information on the selection of the most popular skills from the Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Professional Education.

An examination of the systems and information resources currently in use by colleges for training planning was carried out. The inadequacies of the current ACS of universities in putting the competency-based approach into practice were noted, and it was confirmed that they needed to be made more functional in light of the updated standards for the caliber of specialized training.

It is concluded that in order to improve the quality of specialized training while taking into account the needs of employers and REGOS, a process for the development and evaluation of competencies must be developed[6-8]. Additionally, the algorithm for planning training and tracking the development of competencies must be improved, and the results of this analysis must be analyzed in order to make necessary

adjustments to the way the training process is organized and to raise the competency of the graduates. The presentation of a cognitive model of competence was made possible by the dearth of information on how the disciplines under study affect one another and how competence is formed.

3 Experimental results and their discussion

The presentation includes algorithms for gathering and analyzing expert data in order to create a competency model and compile a list of the most in-demand talents. It is supported that the cognitive modeling methodology was used to create a cognitive map of competence that illustrates the relationships that emerge between disciplines during the competence creation process. One way to visualize the cognitive map of competence is as a directed weighted graph $G = \langle X, R \rangle$, где $X = \langle K, D, d \rangle$ - set of graph vertices

K - competence, D - disciplines directly impacting competence, d - disciplines indirectly influencing competence, R - a set of edges connecting disciplines with competence and disciplines with each other (Fig. 1). A cognitive model was constructed by an expert survey. The expert group's membership is confirmed to include seasoned instructors from a range of academic fields, prospective employers, administrators from

The competence model is shown in Figure 1 as follows:
 • direct influence, o indirect influence,
 two types of impact relationships:
 direct and indirect.

the university, and recent graduates in their field.

Expert opinions are valued according to a proposed framework. Four steps make up the algorithm that has been created for gathering and processing expert data:

1) Experts were surveyed to create matrix W , which establishes how different disciplines D directly form competence K , and matrix V , which establishes how disciplines D indirectly form competence K :

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} W_{D_1K_1} & W_{D_1K_2} & \dots & W_{D_1K_m} \\ W_{D_2K_1} & W_{D_2K_2} & \dots & W_{D_2K_m} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ W_{D_nK_1} & W_{D_nK_2} & \dots & W_{D_nK_m} \end{bmatrix}, \text{ moreover } V = \begin{bmatrix} V_{d_1D_1} & V_{d_1D_2} & \dots & V_{d_1D_k} \\ V_{d_2D_1} & V_{d_2D_2} & \dots & V_{d_2D_k} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ V_{d_tD_1} & V_{d_tD_2} & \dots & V_{d_tD_k} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$W_{D_1K_j} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{forms } D_1 \text{ } \\ 0 & \text{otherwise } \end{cases} K_j, V_{d_1D_t} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{forms } d_1 \text{ } \\ 0 & \text{otherwise } \end{cases} D_t.$$

$s = \overline{1, l}, t = \overline{1, k}, l$ is the number of disciplines d that influence discipline D_1 , k is the number of disciplines that directly influence competencies.

$i = \overline{1, n}, j = \overline{1, m}, m, n \sim$ number of studied disciplines, t - number of formed competencies

- 2) Disciplines are ranked by experts based on how much of an impact they have on competency.
- 3) The concordance coefficient is calculated to verify if the opinions of experts are consistent.

4) The weights of the influence of the competence's constituent parts on its formation are determined using the Fishburn rule. Following data processing, the matrices W and V are converted into matrices R and Q, which include the weights of the disciplines' influence on competence and disciplines' influence on discipline[9-10]:

$$R = \left\| r_{D_i K_j} \right\|,$$

Where $r_{D_i K_j}$ — the weight of the influence of disciplines D_i on competence K_j , where $\sum_{i=1}^n r_{D_i K_j} = 1$

$$Q = \left\| q_{d_s D_t} \right\|,$$

Where $q_{d_s D_t}$ — the weight of the influence of disciplines D_t on competence K_j , where $\sum_{s=1}^l q_{d_s D_t} = 1$

The developed competency model can be supplemented with weighting coefficients to be presented as an orientated weighted graph. The created model serves as the foundation for creating a competency passport and a process for evaluating it. A series of study disciplines can be formed through the application of graph theory techniques (graph traversal in breadth, graph traversal in depth), which is essential for creating curricula.

An algorithm has been created to determine a group of the most sought-after competencies from those listed in the WGES in order to confirm the demand for competencies. Employers from top businesses and organizations in need of skilled professionals in this training field were surveyed. Combining competencies into groups and performing an analysis in each category is advised. The following groups are included in the WGES for the training field "Information Security": general cultural and professional competences, operational competencies, design and technological competencies, organizational and managerial activities, and experimental research activities.

1. Using the paired comparison method to process expert data: Boolean variables are used to express the desire for competencies in a binary preference matrix. Out of k responders, each l -th expert assesses the significance of competence. K_i , with the value b_{ij} (based on the Harrington scale), matrix A describes how each expert evaluated the group's competencies:

$$A^l = \{a_{ij}^l\}_{i,j=1}^n, \text{ otherwise } a_{ij}^l = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{form } b_{ij} \geq b_{ji} \\ 0, & \end{cases}$$

2. The matrices of assessments of all experts are summed up:

$$C = \sum_{l=1}^k A^l = \{c_{ij}\}_{i,j=1}^n.$$

3. An evaluation matrix of the importance of group competencies is introduced:

$$A = \{a_{ij}\}_{i,j=1}^n \text{ где } a_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{если } c_{ij} \geq c_{ji} \\ 0, & \text{иначе} \end{cases}.$$

4. The demand for each competence $S_{(K_1)}$ is determined by summing the Boolean variables along the corresponding row of the matrix:

$$S_{K_1} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{i,j}$$

5. A vector is formed $S = \{S_{K_1}\}$, according to the elements of which, according to the majority rule, a list of the most in-demand competencies is formed: $C_v = \{K_1, K_2, \dots, K_m\}$, determining the priorities of disciplines in the process of further planning of the variable part of the main educational program[11-13].

Competence is considered as a system and its system characteristics are introduced. A procedure for assessing the level of formation of competence in a student in the learning process has been developed, consisting of two stages:

Competence integrity, which evaluates the impact of the collection of disciplines that comprise the competence structure on its formation, and the degree of significance of each discipline on the formation of competence are two system characteristics that can be introduced through the use of graph representation of competence. Using the entropy method, a measure is presented that considers the extent to which disciplines

impact competency. Entropy, which has values between 0 and 1, is defined as the degree of possibility of controlling the development of competence while accounting for the influence of disciplines. The following formula is suggested for determining competence's Shannon's entropy:

$$H = \sum_{j=1}^m p_j(j) \log_2 P_j$$

where p_j is the probability of the influence of discipline on competence. Mutual influence of disciplines on competence

$$H_{63} = H_0 - H,$$

form $H_0 \sum_{i=1}^n H_i$, H_i - discipline entropy, n is the number of disciplines.

The value of participation of each discipline in the formation of competence α , averaged over all disciplines, is introduced:

$$\alpha = \frac{H_0 - H}{H_0}, \text{ где } 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$$

The conclusion is made: the closer to one, the more the entire set of disciplines participates in the formation of competence. In order to determine the degree of influence of each discipline, the average degree of influence of the discipline D_i on competence is determined:

$$H_{D_1} = \frac{H_0 - H}{H_0}, \text{ где } 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$$

where, assuming that the discipline state D_i is fixed, $H_{(D_1)}$ is the average entropy of competence. Considering all chains of influence, $p_i(j)$ is the likelihood that the i -th discipline is in the j -th state.

$$H_j(D_i) = \sum_j p_j \log p_j$$

Considering each chain of impact, p_j is the probability of a discipline's influence on competence, and $H_1(D_1)$ is the entropy of that influence. Comparative evaluation of the impact of the i -th discipline on competence development:

$$\beta_{D_i} \frac{H - H_{D_i}}{H}, \text{ form } 0 \leq \beta \leq 1$$

The discipline's influence increases with β 's proximity to 1. The values of β are used to calculate the weight of the discipline's influence on competence:

$$\mu_{D_1} \frac{\beta_{D_1}}{\sum_1 \beta_{D_1}}$$

where i represents how many disciplines make up the competency.

A language classifier that creates threshold values α and β based on a statistical experiment was proposed, enabling the discipline to be regarded as "significant" and the competence as "integral." A list of "significant" disciplines is created, the degree of effect of each discipline on the competence is assessed, and the degree of completeness of the composition of disciplines that make up the competence is determined as a consequence of stage I.

In stage two, a generalized criterion based on additive transformation is constructed, and the features of the level of competence formation at the present training moment are evaluated. The selection of a generalized criterion stems from the variety of disciplines that contribute to competence, whereby a student's overall competency is determined by their performance in the discipline and the degree of influence of the discipline. An integral additive criterion is applied in order to evaluate the level of competence formation:

$$B_K \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{D_1} * b_{D_1}$$

$B=(b_{(D_1)}, b_{(D_2)}, \dots, b_{(D_n)})$ - vector, the components of which are the points for the disciplines that form the competence[14-15].

Characteristics of the level of competence formation are proposed (Table 1).

characteristics of the level of competence formation

Names			Purpose
the highest possible assessment of competence at the current moment	the minimum possible assessment of competence at the current moment	Current assessment of competence	Show the current state of competence and the boundary values. Measured in units of the point-rating systems (BPC), принятой в вузе
$B_{K_{\max}} \sum_{i=1}^m B_{K_{\max}D1}$ $B_{K_{\max}} = \mu_{D1} * b_{\max D1}$	$B_{K_{\min}} \sum_{i=1}^m B_{K_{\min}D1}$ $B_{K_{\min}} = \mu_{D1} * b_{\max D1}$	$B_{K_{\min}} \sum_{i=1}^m B_{K_{D1}}$	

Relative assessments of the contribution to competence of the studied disciplines (Table 2) and the loss of competence at the current point in time (Table 3) are proposed.

characteristics of the level of competence development

Names			Purpose
the maximum possible contribution of the studied disciplines	the minimum possible contribution of the studied disciplines	current contribution of the studied disciplines	Shows the relative assessment of the level of competence development. Units of measurement in percent. $I_{\text{mek}}, I_{\text{makc}}, I_{\text{mek}} \in [0,1]$
$I_{K_{\max}} \sum_{i=1}^m \mu_{D1}$	$I_{K_{\min}} \frac{B_{K_{\max}}}{b_{\max}}$	$I_{K_{\max}} \frac{B_{K_{\max}}}{b_{\max}}$	

characteristics of the level of competence development

Names		Purpose
loss of competence at the current moment in time	maximum possible number of losses	Shows loss of competence. Units of measurement - percentages. $\delta_{\text{mech}}, \delta_{\text{max}} \in [0,1]$
$\delta_{K_{\max}} = I_{K_{\max}} - I_{K_{\text{mex}}}$	$\delta_{K_{\max}} = \frac{b_{\max} - b_{\text{mex}}}{b_{\max}}$	

where m is the total number of disciplines studied at a particular moment in time.

The competency model's system features enable us to calculate the weighting coefficients of the disciplines' influence on competency as well as the level of participation of each discipline for the system as a whole. Subsequent competency monitoring, a crucial component of the system that supports management decisions when structuring the learning process, requires the defined mechanism for evaluating the degree of competency formation. The primary duties of organizing and carrying out the primary educational program have been taken into consideration[16-19]:

- 1) creation of the OOP framework;
- 2) curriculum development and the creation of educational assignments for teachers; and 3) oversight of the caliber of specialist training.

When addressing these issues within the framework of using the competence-based approach, the drawbacks are noted. Proposed are algorithms to track the quality of specialized training and the growth of the OOP planning and implementation process.

The competency life cycle notion is presented. Each stage of competence formation can be described by a quantitative evaluation of the degree of its formation, which is passed from stage to stage and is further defined and developed at each stage, thanks to an analogy made between the LCC and the LCC of a technological system. The characteristics of the level of competence formation at every stage of its life cycle

are calculated as part of an algorithm designed to track the quality of specialized training (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Monitoring the level of competence development at all stages of the competence life cycle

It is proposed to use the principle of modularity of existing ACS of the university and expand the function of the subsystem "Management of the educational process" in the part "Planning of educational activities" and "Monitoring the quality of education" based on the newly developed algorithm for expanding the process of planning and implementing the OEP.

The following are the most sought-after competencies for the "Information Security" bachelor's degree program: Culture in general - adherence to the law and moral principles (OK2); - cooperation (OK5); - the capacity to solve problems and accept accountability (OKb); - capacity for self-actualization and self-development (OKI 1);

Professional process, which uses mathematical tools and natural scientific rules to address professional challenges (1/1); use of IT and computer science advancements, as well as backing for the adoption of a set of information security measures (1/2); The process of identifying and removing information that poses a risk (OK8) Utilizing programming technologies to address work-related issues (K 16);

- creating an overview of information security concerns in their activity profile (PK19); creating a set of information security management measures (GZ26); - working on the information security policy's implementation (PK29);

planning a small team's tasks while keeping information security standards in mind (PKZ1). The creation of an evaluation of PC1's proficiency in the training direction "Information Security" throughout the first two years of study served as the basis for confirming the efficacy of the procedures that were established [20-24].

Comparing the results of the control group, which studied in accordance with the second generation state educational standard, the degree of this competency rose by 4.6%. The State Attestation Commission conducted an adequate evaluation of the devised technique for computing competence assessments for 156 skills, or 5 competences for each of the 32 students. The expert assessments and the evaluations derived from the devised approach agreed in 93% of cases.

4 Inconclusion

The inadequacies of the information systems and training planning resources were determined by analyzing the issues with modernizing the educational system. It was proven that the university's ACS needed to be able to do more. From the perspective of the competence approach, a block diagram of the administration of the training organization was created. A cognitive model of competence was created, and an algorithm for gathering and analyzing the expert data required to construct the model was put forth. Based on the paired comparisons method, an algorithm was created to determine a list of the most well-liked talents.

The competency model's system characteristics are determined, and a method for determining their numerical values is created. Building an integral criterion based on an additive transformation yields analytical formulations for evaluating the degree of student competencies. The list of "significant" disciplines used to build the curriculum can be determined using a scaling approach based on a linguistic classifier.

The competency life cycle notion has been presented. An algorithm has been devised to track the degree of competences, which includes a current assessment of the condition of competence. An algorithm for extending the main educational program (OOP) planning process has been developed based on the mathematical and algorithmic processes suggested in the study. Recommendations for reorganizing the information systems and resources now in use for university administration responsibilities have been produced.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар:

1. Сибикина, И.В. Формирование множества наиболее востребованных компетенций специалиста по защите информации / И.В. Сибикина // Вестник Астраханского государственного технического университета. Серия: вычислительная техника и информатика. - 2010. - №2 - С. 197- 201.

2. Аяшухамедов, И.М. Определение степени значимости компетенций специалиста по информационной безопасности /И.М. Ажмухамедов, И.В. Сибикина. //Вестник компьютерных и информационных технологий. - 2011. - №7. - С.54 - 56.
3. Sadullayeva Sh.A., Parmankulov F.N., "EMPLOYMENT OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN THE LABOR MARKET" "Digital transformation and artificial intelligence: problems, innovations and trends" I international scientific – practical conference Tashkent 2024.
4. Sadullayeva Sh.A., Parmankulov F.N., "OFFICIAL SOCIAL RELATIONS IN UNIVERSITY GRADUATES' ADAPTION TO THE LABOR MARKET" "Digital transformation and artificial intelligence: problems, innovations and trends" I international scientific – practical conference Tashkent 2024.
5. Садуллаева Ш.А., Парманкулов., Ф. Н., "ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ СПРОСА МОЛОДЫХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА" ANIQ VA TABIIY FANLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI: MUAMMOLAR VA INNOVATSION YECHIMLAR. Farg'ona 2024.
6. Parmankulov F.N., "PLACEMENT OF GRADUATES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE LABOR MARKET", "SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL", VOLUME 3 ISSUE 10 OCTOBER 2024.
7. Дружинина, Е. С. Предпосылки развития центров трудоустройства и карьеры в системе высшего образования / Е. С. Дружинина // Интеллект. Инновации. Инвестиции. 2022. №5. С. 20-30.
8. Дружинина, Е. С. Проблемы молодежного сегмента российского рынка труда и новые акценты политики поддержки занятости молодежи / О. В. Забелина, А. М. Асалиев, Е. С. Дружинина // Экономика труда. 2021. № 9. С. 985-1002.
9. Серова Л. М., Мазеева К. А. Трудоустройство выпускников по данным мониторинга учреждений профессионального образования // Высшее образование в России. 2013 № 3 С. 20-27.
10. Чердниченко Г. А. Выпускник на рынке труда (по материалам опроса Росстата) // Профессиональное образование и рынок труда. 2019. № 4. С. 94-100.
11. Хасенова, Л.А. Трудоустройство выпускников вузов, участвовавших в
12. программах внешней академической мобильности / Л.А. Хасенова, А.А. Нурмагамбетов, Г.Т. Урханбаева // Вестник университета Туран. 2021. № 2(90). С. 208-215 .
13. Фролова, Е.В. Трудоустройство выпускников российских вузов: проблемы и возможности развития профессиональной идентичности / Е.В. Фролова, О.В. Рогач // Экономика образования. 2021. № 3(124). С. 71- 78.
14. Кириченко Э.В. Экономический анализ факторов спроса молодых специалистов на рабочие места // Нормирование и оплата труда в промышленности. - 2011. - № 3. — 0.5 п
15. Кириченко Э.В. Анализ мотивирующей силы социального пакета по категориям работников // Нормирование и оплата труда в промышленно-сти. - 2011. - № 2. - 0.5 п.л
16. Денисова О.А., Леханова О.Л. Лучшие практики инклюзивного высшего образования в вузах Северо-Западного федерального округа // ВЕСТНИК ЧЕРЕПОВЕЦКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА. 2018. №6. С. 156-161.
17. Бикбулатова А.А. Солдатов А.А. Невская М.В. СОЗДАНИЕ ЦЕНТРОВ СОДЕЙСТВИЯ ТРУДОУСТРОЙСТВУ ИНВАЛИДОВ И ЛИЦ С ОВЗ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ // ВЕСТНИК УГНТУ. НАУКА, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ЭКОНОМИКА. СЕРИЯ: ЭКОНОМИКА. 2015. №3(13). С. 37-39.
18. Druzhinina, E. S. "Factors of increasing the efficiency of employment of university graduates in the modern labor market" V. D. Rozhkov, E. S. Druzhinina Labor and social relations., 2024. vol 1, pp 5-14.
19. Khlopina S.Yu. "Demand and supply in the labor market of the Sverdlovsk region of vocational education specialists" Scientific notes of the P. F. Lesgaft University., 2013. vol.7 pp. 156-158.
20. Krekhovets E.V., Basov V.A. "The role of social capital in employment: a review of literature" Actual problems of economics, sociology and law., 2017. vol. 3. pp. 56-60.

21. Ткач Г.Ф., Беспмятнова М. Прикладной бакалавриат как основной механизм профессионализации высшего образования // Вестник Российского университета дружбы народов. Серия: Информатизация образования. 2016. №3. С. 115-117.
22. Степуть И.С. Стратегическое развитие экономики Арктического макрорегиона и его обеспеченность кадрами со средним профессиональным образованием // Региональная экономика: теория и практика 2016. №11 С. 67-69.
23. Волковская Н.М., Плюснина Л.К., Русина А.В. Мониторинг трудоустройства выпускников в системе оценки деятельности вуза // Теория и практика общественного развития. 2014. №1 С. 25-26.
24. Хлопина С.Ю. Спрос и предложение на рынке труда Свердловской области специалистов профессионального образования // Ученые записки университета им. П. Ф. Лесгафта. 2013. №7 С. 156-158.